

Artificial Intelligence in Education: Teachers' Opinion and Attitude in Secondary Schools in Ondo State, Nigeria

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The study investigated secondary school teachers' opinion and attitude towards the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools for instructional delivery in Ondo State. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The study was also guided by two objectives, two research questions and one research hypotheses. The sample population consisted of 360 secondary school teachers randomly selected from six secondary schools across the three senatorial districts of Ondo State. Two secondary schools were randomly selected in each of the three senatorial districts (Ondo south, central and north) in Ondo State. Sixty teachers were randomly selected from each of the sampled schools, making a total of 360 participants. A self-developed questionnaire titled Secondary School Teachers' Opinion and Attitude towards the Use of Artificial Intelligence Questionnaire (SSTOAAIQ)) was used to collect data for the study. Data collected were analyzed with the use of both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The two research questions were answered with the use of means and standard deviation, while the only one research hypothesis was tested with the use of t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that secondary school teachers' opinion about the use of AI for instructional delivery was positive. It was also revealed in the study that teachers' attitude towards the use of AI was positive. The study further reveals that gender has no significance difference on secondary school teachers' opinion about the use of AI for instructional delivery in Ondo State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that secondary school teachers should be encouraged to further develop positive opinion and attitude towards the use of AI for instructional delivery. Also, both male and female teacher should be motivated further to develop positive opinion about the use of AI for instructional delivery in Nigeria particularly in Ondo State.

Keywords:
Teachers' opinion,
Artificial intelligence,
Attitude,
Ondo State

Introduction

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a transformative force in education has become one of the most significant developments in the 21st century. According to Kadaruddin (2023), AI is an application of intelligent systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human Intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, problem-solving, and decision-making. Jones

& Brown (2021) also describe AI as a multidisciplinary science with numerous approaches that operates based on the combination of enormous amounts of digital data and intelligent algorithms that let machines "learn" automatically by having the capacity to read and understand guidelines and data so that they analyze and act following logical reasoning and behave in a way that is comparable to humans.

With the increasing sophistication of AI tools and their potential to enhance instructional delivery, there has been growing interest in understanding how educators perceive and utilize these technologies, particularly for instructional delivery.

The traditional classroom environment, which has long relied on teacher-centered pedagogy and manual instructional strategies, is being redefined by the integration of digital technologies. Among these technologies, AI tools such as ChatGPT, Google Bard, Socrative, Gradescope, AI-powered virtual teaching assistants, personalized learning platforms, and intelligent tutoring systems are increasingly being introduced to improve instruction efficiency and quality of instruction (Lawasi, Rohman & Shoreamanis 2024). These tools offer promising benefits, including personalized learning experiences, data-driven instructional planning, automated grading, and enhanced student engagement.

The use of AI tools in education has the potential to revolutionize how teaching and learning are conducted (Mores & Nethravathi 2024). Akgün and Greenhow (2021) also posited that AI can transform traditional pedagogical approaches into more effective and personalized learning environments. Lawasi, Rohman and Shoreamanis (2024) claimed that AI software can track and analyze student performance and identify individual learning pathways. Judijanto et al.; (2024) avert that AI soft wares can be used to identify individuals' learning deficiencies in the course of the study. (Mores & Nethravathi 2024) also claimed that the analysis of large data sets by AI-powered assessment software enables teachers to gain detailed insights into students' academic success, thereby facilitating the optimisation of curriculum development processes.

Teachers are at the core of educational innovation. Their beliefs, opinions, attitudes,

competencies, and readiness play a central role in the adoption and effective use of new technologies (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2010). Teachers' opinions are crucial factors in the successful implementation of AI in education because it is secondary agents of instructional delivery and innovation. Teachers' opinions encompass beliefs and judgments formed about a particular subject. Zawacki-Richter et al.; (2019) emphasized that teachers' opinions about AI might be influenced by their exposure to AI-related professional development, media narratives about AI, or personal experiences with digital platforms. The opinions of secondary school teachers regarding the integration of rapidly developing AI technologies into education are of great significance in guiding their students by supporting their developmental appropriateness and learning gains.

Attitude is another important factor affecting teachers' use of artificial intelligence tools for instructions. Abidoeye (2023) described attitude as an individual's favorable or unfavorable evaluations, feelings, and tendencies toward a particular object or idea. In the context of AI in education, teachers' attitudes are shaped by multiple factors, including familiarity with technology, perceived usefulness, ease of use, fear of job displacement, and the perceived impact on student learning outcomes. Abidoeye (2024) posited that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use determine an individual's intention to use a new technology. Applying this model to secondary school teachers, their attitudes towards AI tools may be influenced by how users perceive these tools to be in improving instructional delivery and how easy they find them to use.

Gender is an essential factor that affecting the use of technology in instructional delivery. Understanding the gender dynamics of AI utilization among secondary school teachers in Ondo Stat is crucial for addressing disparities and

promoting inclusivity in the adoption of AI-driven educational technologies. Gender plays a significant role in shaping teachers' attitudes, perceptions, and behaviors towards AI, reflecting broader societal norms, expectations, and disparities (Agyemang, & Mereku, 2019). Researchers such as Li and Kirkup, (2022) suggest that gender stereotypes and biases may contribute to disparities in the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields, potentially influencing female teachers' access to and use of AI-driven educational resources. Gendered expectations and societal norms regarding academic interests and career aspirations may impact female teachers' confidence and willingness to engage in AI.

However, despite global trends towards the adoption of AI tools in secondary schools, there is a notable research gap in understanding teachers' opinion and attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence tools for instructional delivery particularly in Ondo State. Therefore, this study investigated secondary school teachers' opinions and attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence tools in Ondo State.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid evolution of technology has significantly influenced the global educational sector. In particular artificial intelligence (AI) tools have been recognized for their potential to transform instructional delivery by personalizing learning, automating administrative tasks, and improving educational outcomes. Despite these benefits, the adoption of AI tools in Nigerian secondary schools, especially in Ondo State, appears limited. Understanding teachers' opinion is crucial because their opinions and attitudes often determine the success or failure of educational innovations. However, inadequate research exists on secondary school teachers' opinion and attitude towards the use of AI in

Nigeria particularly in Ondo. Therefore, this study investigates secondary school teachers' opinions and attitudes towards the use of 'artificial Intelligence tools for instructional delivery in Ondo State.

Objectives of the study

The study aims at achieving the following objectives;

- i. determine secondary school teachers' opinions about the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for instructional delivery in Ondo State.
- ii. determine secondary school teachers' attitudes toward the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for instructional delivery in Ondo State.
- iii. determine gender differences on secondary school teachers' opinions on the use of AI tools for instructional delivery in Ondo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

1. What are the opinions of secondary school teachers about the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for instructional delivery in Ondo State?
2. What is the attitude of secondary school teachers towards the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for instructional delivery in Ondo

Research Hypotheses

Only one hypothesis was generated and tested in this study at significance level of 0.05

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in the opinion of secondary school teachers about the use of AI tools based on gender.

Methodology

This study used a descriptive survey design. The study population consisted of all secondary school teachers in Ondo State. The

sample population consisted of 360 secondary school teachers randomly selected from six secondary schools across three senatorial districts in Ondo State (Ondo North, Central, and North). Two schools were randomly selected from each of the three Senatorial Districts, resulting in six schools. Sixty teachers were randomly selected from each of the six schools, for a total of 360 participants. The instrument for this study was the researcher’s self-developed questionnaire titled the Secondary School Teachers’ Opinion and Attitude towards Artificial Intelligence Questionnaire (SSTOAAIQ). The instrument is divided into four sections A-D. Section A focused on demographic information covering the participants’ schools, senatorial districts and gender. Section B consisted of ten question items eliciting information on secondary school teachers’ opinions about the use of artificial intelligence for instructional delivery. Section C focuses on secondary school teachers’ attitudes towards the use of artificial intelligence for instructional delivery. Section D consisted of ten question items that sought information on the challenges of using artificial intelligence for instructional delivery by secondary school teachers. A 4-point Likert Scale response modes:

Strongly Agree (SA = 4), Agree (A = 3), Disagree (D = 2) and Strongly Disagree (SD = 1) was used. Face and content validation of the instrument was carried out by an expert in test measurement and evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundation and Counselling, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti. To ensure that the instrument was accuracy, appropriate and complete for the study. Cronbach’s Alpha was used to determine the instrument’s level of reliability. A reliability coefficient of 0.84 was obtained and this was considered to be high enough to justify the use of the instrument. The data generated for this study were analyzed usings mean scores and standard deviations to answer the research questions raised in the study. The t-test and Pearson product moment correlation were used to test the research hypotheses in this study. All hypotheses were tested at a significance level of 0.05.

Results

Research Question1: What are the opinions of secondary school teachers about the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for instructional delivery in Ondo State?

Table 1 Secondary school Teachers’ Opinions about the use of Artificial Intelligence

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D
AI can help teachers with administrative task	113	110	87	50	2.79	1.03
AI enhances students learning outcomes	98	122	80	60	2.71	1.04
AI can provide personalized learning for students	136	95	85	44	2.89	1.04
AI can replace teachers in the future	55	93	129	83	2.33	.99
AI may be too complex for the teachers to use	94	135	81	50	2.75	.99
AI should be integrated to teachers’ training	125	98	87	50	2.82	1.05
AI will change the way I teach	83	125	88	64	2.63	1.02
I think AI has the potential to revolutionarise education	134	77	85	64	2.78	1.12
I am interested in learning AI and its application	120	92	90	58	2.76	1.08
I am positive about the use of AI in Education	80	141	85	54	2.68	.98

Key; SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree

Decision Value: *Not Accepted*=0.00-2.44, *Accepted* = 2.45-4.00

From Table 1, the teachers’ responses showed that most items had mean scores above the decision value of 2.45, indicating acceptance. Specifically, teachers agreed that AI can help with administrative tasks (mean = 2.79), enhance students’ learning outcomes (mean = 2.71), provide personalized learning for students (mean = 2.89), and should be integrated into teacher training (mean = 2.82). Teachers also acknowledged that AI may be complex to use (mean = 2.75) but still expressed interest in learning about AI and its applications (mean = 2.76). However, the item “AI can replace teachers in the future” had the lowest mean score (mean = 2.33), which fell below the decision value,

suggesting that teachers do not believe AI will take over their roles. Overall, the results suggest that secondary school teachers in Ondo State have positive opinions on the use of AI in education. They believe that AI has the potential to improve instructional delivery, revolutionize education, and support teaching processes, although they remain cautious about the possibility of AI replacing teachers.

Research Question2: What is the attitude of secondary school teachers’ towards the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for instructional delivery in Ondo State?

Table 2 *Secondary School Teachers’ Attitude towards the Use of AI for Instructional Delivery*

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D	
I feel confident in my ability to use AI tools for instructional delivery	108	114	84	54	2.76	1.04	
I believe AI can enhance my instructional delivery	142	125	93	0	3.13	.79	
AI tools are useful for teaching and learning	126	119	68	47	2.90	1.02	
AI can help me create more engaging lessons	126	124	74	36	2.94	.97	
AI can assist me in assessing my student accurately	121	131	67	41	2.92	.98	
I worry that AI may replace teachers in futures	112	123	73	52	2.81	1.03	
I am concerned about technical issues that may arise when using AI tools for instructional delivery	108	138	76	38	2.87	.95	
I believe AI can reduce teachers’ workloads	109	115	86	50	2.78	1.02	
AI can help teachers provide more personalized feedback to students	138	132	90	0	3.13	.78	
AI can help teachers identify knowledge gaps in students	152	129	79	0	3.20	.77	
Weighted Average						2.94	

Key; SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree

Decision Value: Negative=0.00-2.44, Positive = 2.45-4.00

Table 2 presents the responses of secondary school teachers regarding their attitudes towards the use of AI tools for instructional delivery. The results showed that teachers generally expressed a positive attitude toward AI in teaching and learning, with a weighted average mean of 2.94, which is above the decision value of 2.45. Specifically, teachers strongly agreed that AI can help them identify knowledge gaps in students (mean = 3.20), and provide more personalized feedback to learners (mean = 3.13). They also believed that AI could enhance instructional delivery (mean = 3.13) and create more engaging lessons (mean = 2.94). Similarly, teachers recognized the usefulness of AI tools in teaching and learning (mean = 2.90) and their role in assisting with accurate student assessment (mean = 2.92). However, several concerns

have been raised. Teachers expressed worry that AI might eventually replace teachers in the future (mean = 2.81), and many were also concerned about potential technical issues when applying AI tools in instructional delivery (mean = 2.87). Confidence in their own ability to use AI tools was moderate (Mean = 2.76), and there was agreement that AI could reduce teachers' workload (mean = 2.78). In summary, the findings suggest that teachers in Ondo State generally view AI positively and acknowledge its potential to improve teaching and learning, especially in personalizing and identifying learning gaps.

Hypothesis Testing

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the opinions of secondary school teachers regarding the use of AI tools based on gender.

Table 3 Summary of T-test Showing Difference in Male and Female Teachers' Opinion about the Use of AI Tools

Grouping Variable (Gender)	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	T	Sig.	Remark
Male	137	27.15	2.95	358	-.198	.843	Not Rejected
Female	223	27.21	3.05				

Table 3 shows the differences between male and female secondary school teachers' opinions on the use of AI tools for instructional delivery. The results indicated that male teachers ($\bar{x} = 27.15$) and female teachers ($\bar{x} = 27.21$) reported very similar mean scores. The t-test result ($t = -0.198$, $df = 358$, $p = .843$) was not statistically significant at the level 0.05. This means that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female teachers

regarding the use of AI tools. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho1) is not rejected.

Discussion of Results

The findings of the study showed that secondary school teachers' opinions on the use of AI tools for instructional delivery were positive. The majority of teachers responded positively to all question items on teachers' opinions. The findings of the study agrees with the submission of Alnasib (2023) who

reported teachers' positive opinions on the use of AI for instruction.

With respect to teachers' attitudes towards the use of AI for instructional delivery, the study revealed that secondary school teachers in Ondo State have a positive attitude towards the use of AI for instructional delivery. The study discovered that secondary school teachers in Ondo State generally view AI positively and acknowledge its potential to improve their teaching and learning. This finding is inline with Abidoye (2023) who reported teachers' positive attitude towards the use of technology in practical teaching practice.

The findings of the study also revealed no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers' opinions on the use of AI. This result agrees with the findings of Adelokun and Abidoye (2024) who founds no significant gender difference in students' opinions about the use of technology in instructional delivery in tertiary institutions.

Conclusion

In summary, as Nigeria seeks to harness the potential of AI tools in education, the perspectives of secondary school teachers cannot be overlooked. Their opinions and attitudes are central to a successful AI integration. Understanding how these teachers view and respond to AI tools will provide crucial insights into policy, training, and technological deployment. The Ondo State, with its history of educational innovation, provides an ideal context for examining these dynamics.

By focusing on this region, this study not only highlights local experiences but also contributes to the broader discourse on how developing nations can adapt AI tools for sustainable educational development. As

such, the findings will have implications beyond Ondo State, serving as a reference for other states and stakeholders aiming to modernize instructional delivery in secondary education.

Recommendations

1. Secondary school teachers should be encouraged to develop more positive opinion and attitude towards the use of AI for instructional delivery in Nigeria especially in Ondo.
2. Both male and female secondary schoolteachers should be further motivated to develop positive opinions about the use of AI for instructional delivery in Ondo State and Nigeria.

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